

Microwave Moisture Sensor for Rapid and Nondestructive Grading of Peanuts

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Abstract— A low-cost microwave moisture sensor operating at a single frequency for instantaneous and nondestructive determination of moisture content in peanut kernels from microwave dielectric measurements on peanut pods was developed and tested. The sensor operates at a frequency of 5.8 GHz and uses the principle of free-space transmission measurement of the dielectric properties. Moisture content is determined independent of bulk density with a permittivity-based algorithm.

I. INTRODUCTION

Water is an important component of many natural and man-made products. Water content, or moisture content, is often used to assess the quality of a product and its optimum handling and processing conditions. In agriculture, moisture content is the single most important factor determining the proper time for harvest and optimum conditions for safe storage, and it is used for price determination. With the advent of precision farming and highly automated and computerized agricultural processes, there is a growing need for rapid determination of moisture content. For peanuts, rapid methods for moisture assessment are essential in minimizing aflatoxin risk during storage, maintaining kernel quality, and improving profitability for peanut growers. During the grading of peanuts, determining moisture content in peanut kernels is a tedious and lengthy procedure. It involves collecting pod samples, cleaning foreign materials from the samples, and shelling and cleaning the shelled peanuts before testing the peanut kernels for moisture content.

The purpose of this research is to determine peanut kernel moisture content without having to shell the peanut pods. A novel, low-cost microwave moisture sensor operating at a single microwave frequency was built with off-the-shelf components and tested for moisture determination in peanut kernels from microwave dielectric measurements on pods. The sensor uses the principle of free-space-transmission for measuring the real and imaginary parts of the relative complex permittivity $\epsilon = \epsilon' - j\epsilon''$. Moisture content is determined independent of bulk density with a permittivity-based algorithm [1]. It is customary to use sophisticated and expensive instruments such as impedance and vector network analyzers for accurate determination of the two components of the complex permittivity. In this presentation, an inexpensive microwave circuit is described for determining the real and imaginary parts of the relative complex permittivity from

measurements of the attenuation and phase shift of a microwave signal after it propagates through the sample material. Performance of the microwave moisture sensor is shown here for peanut kernel and pods samples.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Microwave Circuit

Many techniques can be used for measuring the dielectric properties of a given material [2-3]. Among these, free-space techniques (reflection and transmission) have the advantages of being nondestructive, not requiring any sample preparation, and not requiring any physical contact with the material [4]. The microwave moisture sensor described here is based on a free-space transmission technique in which ϵ' and ϵ'' are determined from measurement of the attenuation and phase shift the incident wave undergoes when propagating through the material. Fig. 1 shows the diagram of the microwave moisture sensor with the material sample placed between transmitting and receiving antennas.

Fig. 1. Diagram of microwave moisture sensor.

B. Attenuation and Phase Shift Determination

Attenuation and phase shift are determined by comparing the reference microwave signals measured without the sample to those obtained after the sample is placed between the two antennas.

Attenuation is the difference between the power levels without the sample ($P_{RF,0}$) and with the sample ($P_{RF,S}$) between the transmitting and receiving antennas:

$$\Delta A(\text{dB}) = P_{RF,S}(\text{dB}) - P_{RF,0}(\text{dB}) \quad (1)$$

Phase shift characterizes the delay in propagation caused by the slowing of the wave propagation in the medium. The phase shift is calculated as the difference between the phase measured without the sample (θ_0) and with sample (θ_s) as:

$$\Delta\theta(\text{rad}) = \theta_s - \theta_0 \quad (2)$$

To avoid effects of multiple reflections within the sample and between the antennas through the sample, the material thickness is often selected to ensure a minimum of 10 dB attenuation. An ambiguity in phase determination occurs when the thickness is greater than the wavelength in the material and there is need for a phase correction. The actual phase shift is expressed as:

$$\Delta\theta_{\text{actual}}(\text{rad}) = (\theta_s - \theta_0) - 2\pi n \quad (3)$$

where n is an integer to be determined. Solutions for resolving the phase ambiguity have been proposed [5-6].

C. Computation of Dielectric Properties

The dielectric properties, real and imaginary parts of the relative complex permittivity, $\epsilon = \epsilon' - j\epsilon''$, are calculated assuming a low-loss dielectric ($\epsilon'' \ll \epsilon'$) from measured attenuation and phase shift as follows:

$$\epsilon' = \frac{\beta^2 - \alpha^2}{\beta_0^2} \quad (4)$$

$$\epsilon'' = \frac{2\alpha\beta}{\beta_0^2} \quad (5)$$

where:

$$\alpha(\text{Np/m}) = \frac{\Delta A}{8.686d} \quad (6)$$

$$\beta(\text{rad/m}) = \beta_0 + \frac{\Delta\theta_{\text{actual}}}{d} \quad (7)$$

$$\beta_0 = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda_0} \quad (8)$$

$$\lambda_0 = \frac{c}{f} \quad (9)$$

where λ_0 is the free-space wavelength, c is the speed of light in vacuum in m/s and f is the frequency in Hertz. Both ΔA and $\Delta\theta_{\text{actual}}$ are taken as positive numbers.

III. MICROWAVE MOISTURE SENSOR

Microwave components and related accessories are housed in an 18 in by 12. by 16-inch high aluminum cabinet of rectangular cross-section composed of two parts, a base cabinet and a cabinet cover. The base cabinet, which is a closed rectangular box about 18 inches wide, 12 inches deep, and 5 inches high, houses the microwave circuit components, fused power switch, power supply, cooling fan, and analog-to-digital interface, and serves as a mounting platform for the transmitting and receiving antennas, which face each other in alignment with L-shaped mounting brackets spaced 11-1/2 inches apart above the base cabinet. Figs. 2 and 3 show general views of the microwave moisture sensor and sample holder. A 1/2-in PVC top for the cabinet cover has an opening to receive the sample holder registering the sample in proper position between the antennas for measurements. The entire interior of the antenna chamber was lined with 3/4-inch microwave absorber to prevent any reflections in that chamber which might interfere with the measurement.

Fig. 2. Microwave moisture sensor without upper cabinet cover.

Fig. 3. Microwave moisture sensor and polycarbonate sample holder bucket filled with peanut pods.

IV. MOISTURE CONTENT DETERMINATION INDEPENDENT OF BULK DENSITY

Fig. 4 shows the complex-plane representation of the dielectric properties divided by bulk density for peanut kernels and peanut pods at 20 °C. For both kernels and pods, a linear relationship results, which can be fitted with a linear regression as:

$$\frac{\epsilon''}{\rho} = a_f \frac{\epsilon'}{\rho} + b \quad (10)$$

Where a_f is the slope and b is the intercept. a_f was 0.559 and 0.536 for kernels and pods respectively, and b was -2.501 for kernels and -1.734 for pods respectively. The coefficient of determination was 0.992 for kernels and 0.965 for pods.

Fig. 4. Complex-plane representation of the dielectric properties each divided by bulk density for peanut pods and peanut kernels at 5.8 GHz and 20 °C.

Fig. 5. Variation of density-independent calibration function ψ with moisture content in peanut pods and kernels at 5.8 GHz and 20 °C.

Once the material is poured into the sample holder and placed between the antennas, moisture content is determined with a density-independent calibration function [7] expressed in terms of ϵ' and ϵ'' as:

$$\psi = \sqrt{\frac{\epsilon''}{\epsilon'(a_f \epsilon' - \epsilon'')}} \quad (11)$$

where a_f is the slope determined from the complex-plane representation of the dielectric properties, each divided by bulk density. The relationship between ψ and moisture content for peanut kernels and peanut pods is illustrated in Fig. 5. The linear correlation between calibration function ψ and moisture content in the peanut pods and peanut kernels can be described with linear regressions as follows:

For peanut pods

$$\psi_p = 0.0257M_p + 0.0353 \quad r^2 = 0.977 \quad (12)$$

For peanut kernels

$$\psi_k = 0.0236M_k + 0.0309 \quad r^2 = 0.983 \quad (13)$$

Moisture content in peanut pods and peanuts kernels can be determined by solving equations (12) and (13) for M_p and M_k , respectively.

It is possible to obtain moisture content in peanut kernels by performing microwave measurements on peanut pods. By equating equation (12) to equation (13) the moisture content in peanut kernels is expressed as:

$$M_k = \frac{\psi_p - 0.0309}{0.0236} \quad (14)$$

Use of equation (14) provided moisture content in kernels with a standard error of calibration of 0.9%.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors thank Micah A. Lewis and Murat S. McKeown for conscientious assistance in taking the necessary measurements.

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